

The preparation of L,L-aspartame citric amide†

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Mono-substituted L,L-aspartame citric amide **1** was prepared via coupling L,L- α -BMAP **3** with 1,2-dibenzyl citrate **2** prepared from selective hydrolysis of tribenzyl citrate **5**.

Aspartame is the most widely used non-nutritive sweetener worldwide and is particularly important for soft drinks¹. Citric acid is widely used as an additive along with aspartame. It has been found that dry blends of citric acid and aspartame may form trace amounts of citric acid amides on blending. Citric amides are usually prepared by coupling a protected citric acid and an amine². Several selectively protected citric acids have been obtained, including the formation of a 1,3-dioxolan-4-one ring in citric acid^{2a,3} or using an ester as a protecting group^{2b,4}. However, the use of such derivatives for the synthesis of amides suffers from disadvantages in that they are either difficult to deprotect, or use methoxycarbonyl as a protecting group. Previous works on dibenzyl or diallyl esters of citric acid have utilized initial 1,3-dioxolan-4-one ring formation from citric acid which can also cause difficulty when ring opening is desired^{2a,5}. We now report that selective hydrolysis of tribenzyl citrate to 1,2-dibenzyl citrate **2** and subsequent coupling with L,L- α -BMAP **3** afford a mono-substituted citric amide **1**.

Tribenzyl citrate **5** was obtained by refluxing citric acid and benzyl alcohol in toluene, with azeotropic removal of the water, under the catalysis of HCl⁶. Although the yield was excellent (83%), the reaction time was long (4 days).

We changed the solvent from toluene to xylenes and decreased the reaction time to 12 h, with the yield improved to 95%. Tribenzyl citrate **5** was converted into 1,2-dibenzyl citrate **2** by selective hydrolysis: 0.1 N aqueous NaOH solution was added dropwise to a THF solution of compound **5** at room temperature to afford 1,2-dibenzyl citrate **2** in 45% yield (45% of the starting material **5** could be recovered) (Scheme 1).

Amine **3** could be obtained by the coupling of *N*-*t*-Boc-L-Asp β -benzyl ester **6** and L-phenylalanine methyl ester hydrochloride salt **7** to give **8**, followed by removal of the Boc protective group (Scheme 2)⁷. Coupling of amine **3** with 1,2-dibenzyl citrate **2** in THF with DCC afforded the desired compound **9** in 30% yield, but **9** obtained in this way was difficult to purify (Scheme 2). However, by coupling 1,2-dibenzyl citrate **2** and amine **3** in the presence of isobutyl chloroformate and *N*-methylmorpholine in THF, compound **9** was obtained in 56% yield and the purity was greater than 95%. Hydrogenation of compound **9** in a Parr apparatus afforded target compound **1** in 88% yield. No attempt was made to separate the two diastereoisomers of amide **1** which is a 1 : 1 mixture of the two epimers as shown by the ¹H NMR of compound **9**.

Scheme 1

†Dedicated to Professor D. Nasipuri on the occasion of his 75th birth anniversary

Scheme 2. Reagents and condition : (i) *N*-Methylmorpholine, isobutyl chloroformate, -15° , 3 h, RT, overnight, (ii) HCl/EtOAc (2*M*), RT, overnight; OH^{-} , (iii) DCC/THF or isobutyl chloroformate, *N*-methylmorpholine, THF, (iv) H_2 , Pd/C, MeOH, 40 psi, RT, 6 h.

In conclusion, we have demonstrated the viability of a convergent and highly efficient approach to synthesize citric amide 1. In this synthetic sequence, the crucial step is the selective hydrolysis of tribenzyl citrate 5 to obtain 1,2-dibenzyl citrate 2.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined with a Kofler hot-stage apparatus without correction. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 or $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ at 300 and 75 MHz, respectively, on a Varian VXR-300 NMR spectrometer with TMS ($\delta = 0.00$ ppm) as the internal reference for ^1H NMR and the central line of CDCl_3 ($\delta = 77.0$ ppm) or $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ ($\delta = 39.5$ ppm) as the reference for ^{13}C NMR. Chemical shifts (δ) are reported in ppm downfield from TMS. Microanalyses were performed on a Carlo-Erba 1106 elemental analyzer.

Tribenzyl citrate (5) : Citric acid (43 g, 0.22 mol) was suspended in a mixture of benzyl alcohol (50 ml) and xylenes (200 ml). HCl was bubbled into the reaction mixture during reflux for 12 h. A Dean-Stark apparatus was used to remove the water formed during the reaction. Then benzyl alcohol and xylenes were removed *in vacuo* to give an oil (98 g, 95%). This oil was pure and no further purification was needed for the preparative purpose : ^1H NMR δ 7.40–7.20 (15H, m), 5.08 (2H, s), 5.05 (4H, s), 2.96–2.81 (4H, m); ^{13}C NMR δ 173.0, 169.3, 135.2, 134.9, 128.4, 128.3, 1228.2, 126.8, 73.2, 67.9, 66.6, 43.2.

1,2-Dibenzyl citrate (2) : An aqueous solution of NaOH (0.1 *N*; 600 ml) was added dropwise to a solution of tribenzyl citrate (5; 54 g, 0.12 mol) in THF (900 ml) at room temperature. The mixture was then stirred for 1 h. THF was removed *in vacuo* and the residue water solution was extracted with ethyl acetate. (Tribenzyl citrate can be recovered from this solution). After separation, the aqueous layer

was neutralized by 2 *N* HCl to pH 2–3 and extracted using ethyl acetate. The separated ethyl acetate layer was washed with H_2O (2 \times 200 ml) and saturated brine (200 ml), dried (Na_2SO_4) and concentrated to yield a white solid (19.1 g, 44%), m.p. 75–78 $^{\circ}$; ^1H NMR δ 7.40–7.25 (10H, m), 5.15 (2H, s), 5.07 (2H, s), 2.98–2.81 (4H, m); ^{13}C NMR δ 172.9, 169.4, 135.3, 134.9, 128.6, 128.4 (2), 128.3 (2), 73.1, 68.2, 67.0, 66.9, 43.2, 42.9.

***L,L*-*N*-*t*-Boc-Asp(OBz)-PM (8)** : Isobutyl chloroformate (6.97 g, 51 mmol) was added dropwise over a 15 min period to a solution of *N*-*t*-Boc-L-Asp β -benzyl ester (6; 16.2 g, 50 mmol) and *N*-methylmorpholine (10.1 g, 100 mmol) in THF (300 ml) at -15° . The mixture was then stirred for 15 min when it became a white slurry. *L*-Phenylalanine (7; hydrochloride salt; 10.8 g, 50 mmol) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred at -15° for 2 h, then at room temperature overnight. THF was evaporated ($<40^{\circ}$) and ethyl acetate (300 ml) was added. The mixture was cooled in an ice-bath and saturated NaHCO_3 (100 ml) was added slowly. The separated ethyl acetate layer was washed with saturated NaHCO_3 (2 \times 100 ml), H_2O (100 ml), 70% of citric acid (3 \times 100 ml) and saturated brine (100 ml), dried (Na_2SO_4), and concentrated ($<40^{\circ}$) to yield a white solid (22.5 g, 93%), m.p. 60–61 $^{\circ}$ (Found : C, 64.33; H, 6.78; N, 5.75. $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{32}\text{N}_2\text{O}_7$ calcd. for : C, 64.45; H, 6.66; N, 5.78%); ^1H NMR δ 7.40–7.25 (8H, m), 7.16–7.14 (2H, m), 6.97–6.93 (1H, m), 5.68–5.64 (1H, m), 5.19–5.10 (2H, m), 4.86–4.79 (1H, m), 4.55 (1H, br s), 3.69 (3H, s), 3.12–3.02 (3H, m), 2.80–2.67 (1H, m), 1.44 (9H, s); ^{13}C NMR δ 171.6, 171.3, 170.3, 155.3, 135.6, 135.3, 129.2, 128.5, 128.3, 128.2, 128.1, 127.0, 80.4, 66.7, 53.4, 52.2, 50.4, 37.8, 36.0, 28.2.

***L,L*-Asp(OBz)-PM hydrochloride (3)** : *L,L*-*N*-*t*-Boc-Asp(OBz)-PM (8; 19.4 g, 40 mmol) dissolved in a solution of 2.4 *N* HCl in ethyl acetate (85 ml) was stirred at room temperature overnight. The solvent was evaporated ($<40^{\circ}$)

to give a semi-solid which was triturated and washed with ether (3×50 ml) to yield a solid (16.2 g, 96%), m.p. 146–148° (Found : C, 59.36; H, 6.03; N, 6.57. C₂₁H₂₅N₂O₅Cl calcd. for : C, 59.93; H, 5.99; N, 6.66%); ¹H NMR δ 8.53 (3H, s), 8.16 (1H, d, *J* 6.6 Hz), 7.30–7.21 (10H, m), 5.05–4.95 (2H, m), 4.80–4.65 (2H, m), 3.46 (3H, s), 3.34–3.00 (4H, m); ¹³C NMR δ 171.2, 170.7, 167.7, 135.9, 135.0, 129.3, 128.5, 128.4, 128.3, 128.2, 126.9, 67.3, 54.5, 52.1, 49.7, 37.1, 35.1.

1,2-Dibenzyl-3-L,L-Asp(OBz)-PM citrate (9) : Isobutyl chloroformate (6.0 g, 43 mmol) was added dropwise over 15 min, to a solution of dibenzyl citrate (16.0 g, 43 mmol) and *N*-methylmorpholine (8.7 g, 86 mmol) in THF (250 ml) at –15°. The mixture was then stirred for 15 min when it became a white slurry. L,L-Asp(OBz)-PM hydrochloride (18.0 g, 43 mmol) was added and the mixture was stirred at –15° for 2 h, then at room temperature overnight. THF was evaporated (<40°) and ethyl acetate (300 ml) was added. This mixture was cooled in an ice-bath and saturated NaHCO₃ (100 ml) was added slowly. The separated ethyl acetate was washed with saturated NaHCO₃ (2×200 ml), H₂O (100 ml), 7% of citric acid (3×100 ml) and saturated brine (100 ml), dried (Na₂SO₄) and purified by flash column chromatography on silica gel (30% EtOAc in hexanes as eluent) to give an oil (17.8 g, 56%); ¹H NMR δ 7.45–7.10 (22H, m), 5.20–5.00 (6H, m), 4.90–4.75 (2H, m), 3.65 (1.5H, s), 3.60 (1.5H, s), 3.10–2.50 (8H, m); ¹³C NMR δ 173.0, 171.6 (3), 170.1, 169.7, 168.8, 168.7, 136.0, 135.9, 135.3, 134.9, 129.3, 129.2, 128.5, 128.4, 128.3, 128.2, 127.0, 126.9, 73.8, 73.6, 68.1, 68.0, 66.8 (2), 66.7, 53.7, 53.6, 52.2, 52.1, 49.0, 48.9, 44.7, 44.3, 43.2, 42.4, 37.7, 35.5, 35.4.

1-L,L-Asp(OBz)-PM citrate (1) : 1,2-Dibenzyl-3,L,L-Asp(OBz)-PM citrate (**9**; 15.0 g, 20 mmol) in MeOH (250

ml) was hydrogenated over Pd/C (4%; 3.0 g) in a Parr hydrogenator at 40 psi for 6 h. Pd/C was then removed by filtration and rinsed with methanol (5×200 ml). The combined organic filtrates was concentrated (<40°) to give a white solid, which was washed with ethyl ether and collected by filtration to yield pure product (8.6 g, 90%), m.p. 105–110° (Found : N, 5.66. C₂₀H₂₄N₂O₁₁ calcd. for : N, 5.98%); ¹H NMR (DMSO-D₆) δ 12.20 (4H, br s), 8.31–8.24 (1H, m), 8.13–8.07 (1H, m), 7.40–7.18 (5H, m), 4.61–4.55 (1H, m), 4.50–4.42 (1H, m), 3.58 (3H, s), 3.10–2.85 (2H, m), 2.82–2.40 (6H, m); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-d₆) δ 174.8, 174.7, 171.7, 171.6 (2), 171.5, 170.7, 170.6, 169.5, 169.4, 137.1, 129.2, 128.4, 126.7, 106.1, 73.1, 54.0, 53.9, 51.9, 48.7, 43.5, 43.4, 42.9, 42.5.

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